

Deliverable report for

Funded by
the European Union

Grant Agreement Number 101069888

Deliverable D11.8

“Reports to the European Commission”

Due date of deliverable: 2023/08/31

Actual submission date: 2023/10/20

Identifier:	D11.8: Monitoring and evaluation annual report of communication and dissemination activities (1st release)
Beneficiaries:	CONSORTIUM
Work package/task:	WP11 / Task 11.2
Document status:	draft / final
Confidentiality:	confidential / restricted / public

This project is funded under Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement no 101069888

Lead beneficiary for this deliverable: CSIC - ITQ

Dissemination Level:			
PU	Defined in the DoW	Public	Yes/No
PP		Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	Yes/No
RE		Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	Yes/No
CO		Confidential, only for partners of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	Yes/No

This project is funded under Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement no 101069888

Contents

1. Abbreviations	4
2. Summary	5
3. Communication and dissemination activities	5
3.1 ALL-IN Zero Website	5
3.2 ALL-IN Zero social media	6
3.3 ALL-IN Zero Newsletter	7
3.4 ALL-IN Zero press media.....	8
3.5 ALL-IN Zero video.....	8
3.6 Publications in Scientific Journals.....	8
3.7 Presentations at National and International Scientific Conferences.....	9
3.8 Others	9

1. Abbreviations

CO: Confidential

D: Deliverable

GA: Grant Agreement

2. Summary

This document summarizes the communication and dissemination activities carried out during the first 12 months of the European project ALL-IN Zero, relative to task 11.2. It includes links and images of the project website, press clippings, dissemination activities, social networks, etc.

According to the Grant Agreement (GA) this report will be updated and delivered annually within the deliverables D11.8-D11.11 Reports on monitoring and evaluation of communication and dissemination activities. This is the first delivery, including all communication and dissemination activities executed from month 1 to month 12.

3. Communication and dissemination activities

3.1 ALL-IN Zero Website

The ALL-IN Zero website allinzero.eu is available from the month 6 of the project. The website has been actively maintained during the first 12 months by iPoint (Figure 1). The aim of the website is to increase the recognition of the ALL-IN Zero project to the public.

Google Analytics utilities will be employed from month 12 to the end of the project to monitor the website access: number of visitors, duration of the visits, geographical area, pages of the website more visited, etc.

Figure 1: ALL-IN Zero website home page

3.2 ALL-IN Zero social media

Both the [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#) accounts for the ALL-IN Zero project have been already created and are being used to publish announcement and relevant information of the project (Figure 2 and Figure 3). Official Twitter/LinkedIn accounts and groups have joined to raise awareness among interested stakeholders. The visibility of the social media post of the ALL-IN Zero project is shown in table 1.

Figure 2: ALL-IN Zero Twitter

Figure 3: ALL-IN Zero LinkedIn account

Table 1: Social media visibility

Social Media	Posts	Followers	Impressions
Twitter	6	10	>450

Linkedin	7	51	>3500
----------	---	----	-------

3.3 ALL-IN Zero Newsletter

A newsletter will be produced once a year highlighting project results and milestones. In Figure 4 we can see the first newsletter of the first 12 months of the project, that has been uploaded to the website.

Figure 4: ALL-IN Zero project first Newsletter

3.4 ALL-IN Zero press media

Two press releases have disseminated the ALL-IN Zero project, see table 2.

Table 2. Summary of the press releases which have disseminated ALL-IN Zero project.

Country	Media	Format	Link
Spain (UPV)	Mass media (radio, press)	Press release	https://www.upv.es/noticias-upv/noticia-13804-all-in-zero-va.html
Austria (AVL)	Mass media (radio, press)	Press release	https://www.avl.com/en/press/press-release/avl-participate-development-advanced-integrated-multi-fuel

These press release have been published in different media platforms together with partners' organization websites, ALL-IN zero website and ALL-IN Zero social media.

3.5 ALL-IN Zero video

A video aiming at raising awareness of the project and its expected outcomes is under construction (Figure 5). This video will be used by the partners to present the project, as well as for press relation purposes, considering the general public as the main target audience. The video will include partners' interviews, user's experiences, and the use and validation of ALL-IN Zero technology under laboratory settings. The video will be accessible from the website and could be uploaded in YouTube.

The image shows two screenshots from the ALL-IN Zero LinkedIn account. The left screenshot is titled 'Outlook' and describes the 'ALL-IN Zero promotional video target' as a 5-minute video where each partner contributes. It includes a 'CONCEPT' diagram showing the flow from 'Mechanical energy' and 'Thermal energy' through 'Mechanical power ICE' and 'Electrical Power ICE' to 'H₂O'. It also lists partners like CSIC, JÜLICH, and AVL, and provides project details: Project number: 101069888, Type of action: HORIZON-RIA // Call: HORIZON-CLS-2021-D2-01-08, ALL-IN Zero Project Status, and page number 2.

The right screenshot is titled 'Video description' and lists 'Main video blocks':

- General description of ALL-IN Zero project [20 s] UPV-CMT
- Description of ALL-IN Zero technology (flow diagram) [45 s] UPV-CMT
- Description of the CMR [1.5 m] FZJ / CSIC-ITQ
 - Characteristics and advantages
 - Questions to be solved by the project
- Description of the H₂-ICE [45 s] AVL-I
 - Characteristics and advantages
 - Questions to be solved by the project
- Description of the H₂-FC [45 s] AVL-I
 - Characteristics and advantages
 - Questions to be solved by the project
- Discussion about ALL-IN Zero benefits [1 m] ALL near GA
 - Impact of the project

 It also includes a 'Sub-video structure' section with a 'Partner intro [15-30 s]' and a 'Partner intro [15-30 s]' (repeated) and 'I'm proud to be part of ALL-IN Zero project... ALL-IN zero integration [10 s]' (repeated) and 'ICEs are attractive to decarbonize transportation since they...'. Project details at the bottom match the left screenshot, and the page number is 3.

Figure 5: ALL-IN Zero LinkedIn account

3.6 Publications in Scientific Journals

The partners will publish the project activities and results in different scientific journals. Currently, several publications are being prepared summarizing the first results of ALL-IN Zero project.

3.7 Presentations at National and International Scientific Conferences

The partners have presented the project activities and results at national and international conferences. Table 3 shows the presentations that have already been presented. The website and the social media of the project also collect these contributions.

Table 3. Summary of the press releases which have disseminated ALL-IN Zero project.

Type of Event	Name of Event	Location	Date	Responsibility
Conference	3rd LEC Sustainable Shipping Technologies Forum (LEC SSTF 2022)	Hamburg (Germany)	September 2022	UPV
Conference	Transport Research Arena (TRA 2022)	Lisbon (Portugal)	November 2022	UPV
Conference	V Winter Meeting ITQ	Valencia (Spain)	December 2022	CSIC
Conference	2023 I ² CNER ANNUAL SYMPOSIUM	Kyushu (Japan)	February 2023	FZJ
Conference	98th DKG Annual Meeting	Jena (Germany)	March 2023	FZJ
Conference	eMobility Expo & World Congress	Valencia (Spain)	March 2023	UPV
Conference	MTET workshop	Jülich (Germany)	June 2023	FZJ

3.8 Others

The partners have carried out other dissemination activities that have been summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Summary of the press releases which have disseminated ALL-IN Zero project.

Type of Event	Name of Event	Format	Date	Responsibility
Website	UPV Webpage	Web post	October 2022	UPV
Website	CSIC Webpage (ITQ)	Web post	October 2022	CSIC
Social media	UPV-CMT LinkedIn account	LinkedIn post	February 2023	UPV
Social media	UPV-CMT LinkedIn account	LinkedIn post	May 2023	UPV
Mailling	AVL E-Mobility Newsletter - May 2023	Newsletter	May 2023	AVL
Mailling	AVL Highlights and News - June 2023	Newsletter	June 2023	AVL
Social media	AVL Global LinkedIn account	LinkedIn post	June 2023	AVL
Internal communication	4Weeks AVL Internal magazine	Magazine	June 2023	AVL